

THE IMPORTANCE OF ONLINE EDUCATION AND THE WAYS OF CONDUCTING ONLINE LESSONS EFFICIENTLY

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Abstract: *This article is about the significance of online learning and gives detailed information about effectively conducting lessons while teaching students online. This report contains some ways and methods for improving the condition of our lessons in online learning.*

Keywords: *online education, advanced technologies, traditional education, effective lessons, internet connection.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's contemporary world, advanced technologies are developing at a rapid rate. And also, the need for online education is increasing day by day. We know that during our lives, we feel the necessity for education in every situation. Therefore, deepening this system as well as possible is our primary duty. So, our government is also trying to establish new rules and measures to improve our education system. For instance, the law that was established in 2019 also aims to upgrade the education system until 2030. According to this law, the decision is mainly to confirm the priorities of the reform of the quality of the education system and to bring the process of training personnel with strong knowledge and skills who can think independently and freely to a new level in terms of quality, which includes several directions, such as conducting classes using advanced technologies.

We know that there are two modalities of classes. They are:

1. Traditional classes
2. Online classes

Distance learning is becoming one of our primary needs in today's world. When it comes to the history of online learning, it began in about 1700s. Namely, according to the suggestion of Kaleb Fillips that was sent to the newspaper called Boston in 1728, it was stated that students were interested in studying shorthand in many countries of the world through the exchange of letters. This was the first stage of distance education. Later, this field continued to develop. For example, by 1960, the form of online education began to develop more rapidly with the help of the internationally recognized organization UNESCO. Later, in 1969, for the first time in the world, to unite all educational organizations, the first open-university-Efir University, was established. Attention to this form of education is rising day by day in our country. After all, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted in 2022 "On measures to introduce the distance education system in higher education organizations" is one of them. The purpose of this form of education is to create an opportunity for the students to learn educational programs using active information technologies, regardless of their place of residence, and to develop their professional potential based on the student's interests, needs, and talents.

METHODS

Distance education is organized based on the following conditions:

- The interactivity of class participants;
- Identification of class participants;
- Compliance with pedagogical goals of using information and communication technologies;
- Flexibility and openness of the education process and teaching;

Therefore, if these requirements are fully fulfilled in the form of distance education, the quality of the lessons will be high. Advanced information technologies are considered the most important tool in organizing online classes at a higher educational institution, lyceum, college, and school, and teaching students online. We know that to receive education in the form of distance education, the first thing we

need is an active internet, a computer, or a mobile phone. These tools are one of the most essential technologies that we feel are necessary for distance learning. Therefore, first of all, we are required to prepare an appropriate study room for ourselves and an available computer and Internet. And also some methods can help you to conduct your lessons efficiently. Firstly, when you begin your lessons online you should never forget that you ought to keep in touch with your students to provide their activeness in your lesson. It is clear that learning lessons at home, namely online is a challenging task. However, to have effective lessons for both teachers and students while online education there are some tips and strategies that can help you successfully navigate your online lessons.

- Create an energetic learning environment for yourself. Dr. Hatten who is a member of the USF Instructional Technology faculty recommends that each student who is learning online should choose an environment at their home that is free from different distractions. And the student should make that area her or his workplace.
- Establish a timetable for concluding and reviewing assignments. If you do not have any schedule for your lessons, it will be confusing and makes you bewildered. But when you create a certain timetable you know when you should study that subject or another. Because you establish specific times for your subjects, to work on each class. Not only students should establish a timetable, but also the instructors have to create their ones.

- Affirm the online course's technical requirements. As it has mentioned above, the main difference between online learning and traditional education is that you have to work with modern information technologies while you are learning online. You are required to provide a place, computer, active internet, and other items you need while studying to have a successful online education. You should be aware of technical requirements during online education. Unless you get to know these requirements you should not sign up for any online courses.
- Make your student interested in your lessons. The degree to which a student can pass the lesson depends first of all on his interest in the subject. Arousing interest in lessons, especially among young children, is the most important and first task of a pedagogue. For example, before starting online lessons warning children about the topic to be covered and arousing their interest in this topic ensures that the lesson will be more effective.
- Preparing interesting presentations related to the theme. It is an important task to ensure the activeness of every student in the lesson, and it is the main task of the teacher to share the necessary information with them. If presentations related to the topic are created and used during the lesson, each student will develop a broader understanding of the lesson. And if these presentations are presented to the students at the end of the lesson, they will be able to further expand their knowledge using these presentations outside of the lesson.
- Keep consistent communication with your students. Every teacher is in charge of his or her student's studies. And their responsibility is also to instruct and educate them. Teachers should try to keep in touch with individual students daily. Because we know that being distracted is much easier while learning online than in traditional education. Therefore, instructors should communicate and interact with their students as much as possible to make them engaged in their studies.

RESULTS

After using these kinds of methods while educating online, your lessons will be not only effective but also practical for your students.

As we have mentioned above, there are lots of benefits of online learning:

- It can provide added flexibility and self-paced learning. Not many people can take time off from work to commit to a full-time graduate program. For people who need to juggle working and going to educational places such as schools, universities, colleges, and so on, the flexibility of online learning can provide individuals with the opportunity to learn what they want while they are working or busy with their family members. Namely, the flexibility allows you to balance work, life, and graduate school.

- You can manage your time more efficiently. We know that, while keeping the balance between work, family, and education, commuting to schools is not an easy thing to do. However, if you want to learn lessons online you will be able to have enough time for these three. The particular reason for this circumstance is that you can learn the lessons online wherever and whenever you want. In place of going to study places you can save your precious time and you can spend this time on other important tasks.

- You can enrich your knowledge in terms of IT skills. To go online and start the online lessons you need to know how to use your computer or smartphone as well as possible. You will be given some assignments or coursework during the period of learning online. And of course, you have to use digital learning materials and

websites, and you will get to know new tools and software and so on. And such kinds of situations help you to enhance your computer skills.

- You can broaden your outlook about the world. As you communicate with a lot of people who are from all around the globe while online learning you have an opportunity to get many information about these countries and their nationalities. Discussions that take place in the online lessons can include students from all nations which can enable you to not only broaden your perspective but also become culturally aware.

- There are plenty of course options that can lead to better job prospects. People can easily find high a wide range of courses that are related to their field. With the help of these programs of study, you can develop your abilities in terms of your area. Distance learning can provide these courses for all ages, putting them in control of their advancement and reaching their goals.

- You can spend less money on online learning than on traditional learning. It is clear that getting knowledge, namely education, costs expensive, but with the help of online education, you can save money in several ways. We all have to spend our money on transportation while commuting to our study places. However, if we learn online, we can save the money that is spent on transportation. Additionally, every student who studies in school spends a large amount of money on textbooks, tuition fees, and course materials. In comparison to traditional education, online learning offers virtual resources which are cheaper than these textbooks.

- You can get instant feedback about your results. In online lessons, students upload assignments to get feedback from their professors. As long as professors review students' work they give their feedback electronically. As a result, students can receive feedback right after submitting their work rather than waiting for two or three days.

DISCUSSION

We know that there are several useful platforms such as Moodle, My Teacher, Stem, and so on for creating efficient lessons for students while teaching online. And

the platform of Moodle is one of the most valuable online platforms. There are many opportunities in this online platform for both students and teachers. This platform includes the following:

- Students can get knowledge all day on this platform when the internet works well;
- There are a lot of chances for both students and teachers in terms of time;
- This platform helps you to enhance your knowledge of advanced communication technologies
- On this platform teachers upload some sources related to the topic and they evaluate students' work
- Students study, submit assignments and do tests on this platform

Besides, you can find other useful platforms to continue your study online. For example:

1. iSpring Market
2. Coursera
3. Udemy Business

and other platforms. These platforms offer many benefits for users. First of all, in these platforms teachers, trainers and students can interact with each other which leads the lessons to effectiveness. Moreover, students can study in groups, namely teachers can divide students into small groups during some activities.

CONCLUSION

As you can see teachers can conduct lessons in this platform and other ones in an effective way. The particular reason is that students can get new information about the new topic with the help of the sources, their teacher sent. In addition, they can enrich their sight about this topic by doing tests at the end of lessons. Ultimately, students have a chance to do some assignments which are helpful for their study and after submitting these assignments they can get feedback from their teachers as well. Taking everything into account, students can upgrade their knowledge with the help of online learning without wasting their time. Furthermore, there are lots of relevant information and courses in online education.

REFERENCES:

1. <https://lex.uz/docs/-6221502>
2. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-4545884>
3. Seven benefits of online learning. Graduate programs staff. September 25, 2019.
4. The 10 benefits of online education in a virtual classroom. Drexel university school of education
5. 10 tips for success in online classes. University of South Florida. 2023.
6. X. Ahadjonov Masofaviy ta'lim va uni boshqarish tizimlari. 2021.